

Figure S1. Spectrograms of the light bulb used in the anechoic chamber for all experimental groups (LD, LL2, LL5 and LL). (A) 40 lux, (B) 5 lux, (C) 2 lux. The light spectra were recorded using the Sekonic Spectromaster C-700 (North White Plains, NY, USA).